

The Roles of Religiosity and Empathy in Shaping Pro-Environmental Behaviors and Positive Attitudes toward Animals: A Quantitative Study of Undergraduate and Graduate Students

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Abstract: Recently, the links between pro-environmental behaviors, positive attitudes toward animals, and religiosity have become the subject of numerous studies from various disciplines, both nationally and internationally. The main aim of the study was to determine the link between religiosity and positive attitudes towards animals and pro-environmental behaviors, and to detect the mediating role of empathy in this relation. While existing studies have examined the relationship between religiosity and empathy, pro-environmental behaviors, or attitudes toward animals separately, no research to date has explored these variables together within a single framework or investigated empathy as a mediating factor. This study addresses how religiosity influences empathy, pro-environmental behaviors, and positive attitudes toward animals, and examines the mediating role of empathy in these relationships. In doing so, the study seeks to address a gap in existing literature. The participants of the study consist of 373 undergraduate and graduate students selected through convenience sampling. Of the study group, 54.2% (N=202) are female and 45.8% (N=171) are male, with an average age of 24.9 years (SD=5.75). Among the undergraduate students, 36.9% (N = 110) were enrolled in the Faculty of Theology, 17.4% (N = 52) in the Faculty of Engineering, and 10.0% (N = 30) in the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, while 35.5% (N = 106) were enrolled in other faculties such as Education and Health Sciences. Among the postgraduate students, 65.3% (N = 49) were affiliated with the Institute of Social Sciences, and 34.7% (N = 26) with the Institute of Health Sciences. In this current study, *Religiosity Scale*, *Empathic Tendency Scale*, *Active Environmental Sensitivity Scale* and *Scale for Positive Behaviors towards Animals* were utilized to collect data. Data for this study were collected from university students in Turkey during June and July 2024. The study was conducted during a period in which issues related to stray animals in Turkey were widely debated across various segments of society, coinciding with the enactment of legislation addressing the management of stray animals. The findings obtained from the study using structural equation modeling indicated that religiosity increases empathetic tendencies and pro-environment behaviors, while it decreases positive attitudes towards animals. Additionally, the research findings showed that empathy increases both pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals and that positive attitudes toward animals also clearly affect pro-environmental behaviors. The study also found that empathy plays a mediating role between religiosity and positive attitudes towards animals.

Keywords: Psychology of Religion, Religiosity, Empathy, Pro-Environmental Behaviors, Positive Attitudes towards Animals.

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Dindarlığın ve Empatinin Çevre Dostu Davranışları ve Hayvanlara Karşı Olumlu Tutumları Şekillendirmedeki Rolü: Lisans ve Lisansüstü Öğrenciler Üzerine Nicel Bir Çalışma

Öz: Son yıllarda, çevre yanlısı davranışlar, hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumlar ve dindarlık arasındaki ilişkiler hem ulusal hem de uluslararası düzeyde çeşitli disiplinler tarafından ele alınarak pek çok araştırmanın konusu olmuştur. Bu çalışmanın temel amacı, dindarlık ile hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumlar ve çevre yanlısı davranışlar arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek ve bu ilişkide empati düzeyinin aracılık rolünü ortaya koymaktır. Mevcut literatürde, dindarlık ile empati, çevre yanlısı davranışlar ya da hayvanlara yönelik tutumlar arasındaki ilişkiler ayrı ayrı incelenmiş olmakla birlikte, bu değişkenleri tek bir çerçevede ele alan ve empatinin aracılık rolünü değerlendiren bir çalışmaya rastlanmamıştır. Bu çalışma, dindarlığın empati, çevre yanlısı davranışlar ve hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumlar üzerindeki etkisini incelemekte ve bu ilişkilerde empatinin aracılık rolünü analiz etmektedir. Bu yönüyle çalışma, alan yazındaki bir boşluğu doldurmayı hedeflemektedir. Araştırmanın örneklemini, kolayda örnekleme yöntemiyle seçilen 373 lisans ve lisansüstü öğrenci oluşturmaktadır. Katılımcıların %54,2'si (N=202) kadın, %45,8'i (N=171) erkektir ve yaş ortalaması 24,9'dur (SD=5,75). Lisans öğrencilerinin %36,9'u (N=110) İlahiyat Fakültesi, %17,4'ü (N=52) Mühendislik Fakültesi, %10,0'ı (N=30) İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi öğrencisi iken, %35,5'i (N=106) Eğitim, Sağlık Bilimleri vb. diğer fakültelerde öğrenim görmektedir. Lisansüstü öğrencilerin ise %65,3'ü (N=49) Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, %34,7'si (N=26) Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü'ne kayıtlıdır. Araştırmada veri toplamak amacıyla *Dindarlık Ölçeği*, *Empatik Eğilim Ölçeği*, *Aktif Çevresel Duyarlılık Ölçeği* ve *Hayvanlara Yönelik Olumlu Davranışlar Ölçeği* kullanılmıştır. Veriler, Türkiye'deki üniversite öğrencilerinden Haziran ve Temmuz 2024 tarihlerinde toplanmıştır. Çalışma, Türkiye'de sokak hayvanlarına ilişkin sorunların toplumun farklı kesimleri tarafından yoğun biçimde tartışıldığı ve sokak hayvanlarına ilişkin bir yasanın yürürlüğe girdiği bir dönemde gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmada verilerin analizi SPSS ve AMOS yazılım programları yardımıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma değişkenlerinin basıklık ve çarpıklık değerlerinin -2 ile +2 sınırları içerisinde olduğu ve veri setinin normal bir dağılım gösterdiği anlaşılmıştır. Araştırmada kullanılan ölçeklerin geçerlilik düzeyleri açılımlayıcı ve doğrulayıcı faktör analizleriyle test edilmiş güvenilirlik için Cronbach alfa değerlerinden ve uyum göstergelerinden istifade edilmiştir. Temel hipotezlerin testi ise yapısal eşitlik modellemesine uygun olarak yol analizi kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Yapısal eşitlikçi modelin kullanıldığı araştırmada dindarlık eksojen/dışsal (exogenous) çevreci davranışlar ve hayvanlara yönelik tutum endojen/içsel (endogenous) ve empati ise aracı değişkenler olarak belirlenmiştir. Yapısal eşitlik modellemesi ile elde edilen bulgular, dindarlığın empatik eğilimleri ve çevre yanlısı davranışları artırdığını, buna karşın hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumları azalttığını göstermiştir. Ayrıca, empati düzeyinin hem çevre yanlısı davranışları hem de hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumları artırdığı; hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumların da çevre yanlısı davranışlar üzerinde anlamlı bir etkisi olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Bununla birlikte, empatinin dindarlık ile hayvanlara yönelik olumlu tutumlar arasındaki ilişkide aracılık rolü üstlendiği bulgusuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Din Psikolojisi, Dindarlık, Empati, Çevre Yanlısı Davranışlar, Hayvanlara Yönelik Olumlu Tutumlar.

Introduction

In recent years, individuals' attitudes and behaviors toward the natural environment and animals have been explored from various perspectives across different social science disciplines. Given that religious teachings often shape individuals' interactions with both the environment and animals, these issues are also examined in relation to religiosity. However, relatively little attention has been paid to the mediating factors through which religiosity influences individuals' attitudes toward animals and the environment. Specifically, the question of "which other variables mediate the relationship between religiosity and environmental behaviors or positive attitudes toward animals" has been less thoroughly investigated than the direct correlations between religiosity and these variables (Ayten, 2021). A review of the literature reveals that many different topics have been studied as variables related to individuals' attitudes and behaviors toward animals and the natural environment. Although these issues were not addressed together in the studies, the effects of

religiosity on environmental attitudes and behaviors and attitudes towards animals were examined separately (Çiçek & Ayten, 2023; Hazar, 2023). While discussing the link between religiosity and pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors, the issue of whether religiosity leads individuals to develop a possessive or a stewardship approach towards the environment has been discussed and empirical findings on the subject have been evaluated. In most of the studies, it has been found that religiosity supports a sense of stewardship towards the environment and thus increases individuals' environmentally friendly behaviors (Ayten, 2010).

According to the general perspective of religions, nature is seen as a sacred trust that needs to be protected. Religions have been the source of man's relationship with the environment, based this relationship on a divine and moral basis, and emphasizing that man is not alone in the world of existence (Yıldırım, 2016). For instance, Jewish environmentalists have demonstrated the nature-religion-human interaction by referring to the Old Testament and its Sharia. According to the Jewish understanding of the natural order, the laws of nature are inseparable from the "Will" that has authority over all beings. The unity of human and natural order, cosmic and religious laws, is part of the traditional Jewish worldview (Nasr, 2022). In Christianity, nature is regarded as God's creation and therefore a trust to be protected. The concept of stewardship refers to man's responsibility to protect and care for the world God created. In Christian theology, this responsibility includes the sustainability of nature and the fair use of resources (Attfield, 2018). Islam's understanding of the environment is based on the Qur'an and hadiths. According to these sources, which characterize man as the caliph of the earth (Baqara 2/30), man has a responsibility towards nature and should protect it with a sense of trust (Ayten, 2021). While the religions of the People of the Book have teachings on the human-environment relationship, Far Eastern religions also have many teachings on this subject. In Buddhism, for example, there is the principle of "the whole in the one and the one in the whole; the one is identical to the whole and the many to the one". This principle means that everything can mutually permeate each other. According to these teachings, a Buddhist should not harm life (Bachelor, 1997). In Hinduism, the caste system dominates the social structure, and this system is also reflected in the human-nature interaction. Accordingly, the highest caste includes nature and all animate and inanimate spirits. This can be seen as the reason why Hindu individuals try not to harm nature (Demirci, 1998). The concept of Ahimsa (compassion) has an important place in Hindu theology. Ahimsa means not killing, not hurting, not harming any living thing (Kutlutürk, 2014). Ahimsa can also shape an individual's attitudes towards the environment. The Hindu attitude of not hurting any living being requires active environmentalism (Keçeci, 2021).

When the studies conducted within the framework of religiosity-environmentalism and religion-environmental behaviors are evaluated, it is seen that some studies (Wolkomir et al., 1997) examine the tendency to protect the environment, while others (Bartkowski & Swearingen, 1997) deal with the relationship between religiosity and environmentalism. Especially in the West, most of the studies on this subject theoretically explain environmental problems with the human model and conception in the Judeo-Christian tradition (Ayten, 2021; Eckberg & Blocker, 1989). Relational and empirical studies, on the other hand, discuss the issue within the framework of research findings on

topics such as religiosity and environmentalism, environmentally friendly behaviors, and green consumption. For example, Boyd (1999) examined the relationship between Christian beliefs and environmentalism in America. In this article, it was found that Christian religious beliefs and the behavior of members of this religion weakly affect support for the environment. The study concluded that there are complex and sometimes contradictory relationships between Christianity and environmentalism. According to an article (Ogunbode&Oyekan, 2023) investigating the effects of religious practices on the sustainable urban environment in Nigeria, it was concluded that religious activities have a significant impact on climate change, noise pollution, and consumption of natural resources. In another study (Stanford & Brewer, 2011) conducted on a Christian sample group in the USA, it was found that religiosity has a negative effect on environmentalism through some components (through political conservatism) and a positive effect through other components (through church involvement). Based on this finding, the researchers concluded that the bidirectional effect obscures the impact of religiosity on environmentalism.

In an article (Jenkins & Chapple, 2011) titled “Religion and the Environment”, which deals with the approaches of Eastern and Western religions to nature and ecology in general, the importance of religious dimensions for understanding how ecological and religious systems interact with each other is discussed. As a result, it is concluded that the approach of religious traditions to environmental issues plays a critical role in shaping environmentalist behaviors and that it would be useful to re-evaluate religious teachings from an ecological perspective. A study (Skirbekk et al., 2020) involving Christians, Muslims, Jews, Buddhists, Hindus, Folk religions, Other Religions, and the Non-Religious examined the relationship between religious commitment and environmental change. The study concluded that environmental risks are higher in countries with high levels of religious commitment.

Studies on the relationship between the environment, environmentalism, and religiosity in Islamic countries and Turkey are fewer than those in the West. For example, in a study conducted by Ayten (2009), the relationship between individuals' level of religiosity and their tendencies towards environmental stewardship and environmental behavior was examined. As a result of the study, a positive relationship was found between religiosity and “stewardship orientation” and “waste avoidance”, while a negative relationship was found between “ownership orientation” and “active environmental sensitivity”. In another study (Kavalcı, 2019), a significant positive relationship was found between intrinsically motivated religiosity and waste avoidance, which is one of the sub-dimensions of environmentalism. In a study conducted by Ünal (2010), it was found that religious individuals were more sensitive to environmental problems.

Research on animals has been conducted and continues to be explored from various perspectives across multiple disciplines, including the social sciences (Çelik & Karakaş, 2023; Görgülü, 2019), human sciences (Çiffiliz & Wolfe, 2021), and natural sciences (Altuğ, 2009). Within these studies, the influence of religiosity on individuals' attitudes and behaviors toward animals has been examined in diverse ways. The relationship between animal welfare and religiosity (Hazar, 2023; Sinmez et al., 2015), the relationship between religiosity and animal rights (Aebersold et al.,

2007; Alici, 2020; Armutak, 2012; Çelik& Karakaş, 2023; Peek et al., 1997), the view of religions towards animals (Bayram, 2021), the role of religiosity in reducing crimes against animals (Minton, 2020), the relationship between religiosity and behavior towards animals (Dyczewska, 2008), animal care and ethics (Ottuh & Idjakpo, 2021) can be given as examples. When the studies were examined, it was generally observed that religiosity has different effects on people's attitudes and behaviors toward animals. According to the findings of some studies, it can be said that religiosity has positive effects on behaviors towards animals, while in some studies it has negative effects, and there are also studies in which no significant relationship was found between these two variables (Jalil et al., 2018; Kafalı, 2022).

In recent years, the subject of empathy has started to be studied more in various academic fields (Decety & Moriguchi, 2007). The most important feature of empathy studies in the academic field is that they combine different disciplines and perspectives that try to understand and explain human social development and behavior (King, 2011). The relationships between religiosity and positive attitudes towards animals and empathy, which are the main variables of this article, have also been addressed by many studies separately. In general, it has been found that religiosity has a role in increasing empathic tendency (Ayten, 2009; Karagöz, 2022; Korkmaz&Hacıkeleşoğlu, 2021). Similarly, studies investigating the relationship between attitudes toward animals and empathy have yielded mixed results, with some finding a significant association between the two variables and others reporting no significant relationship. When examining studies on the relationship between one of the key variables of this research—attitudes toward animals and empathy—several prominent themes emerge. These include the association between prosocial and antisocial behaviors toward animals and levels of empathy (Signal & Taylor, 2007), the role of empathy in facilitating communication with animals (Çalışkan et al., 2014), and findings suggesting the limited effectiveness of empathy in shaping human-animal relationships (Daly & Morton, 2003). In a study conducted by Demir and Zeren (2022), it was found that attitudes toward animal rights and prior pet ownership were significant predictors of empathy levels. Demir (2020) in his study on adults found that empathy significantly predict attitudes towards animal rights. Another study examining the relationship between animal welfare and empathy (Graça et al., 2018), explained why women support animal exploitation less than men through the role of empathy. In a study exploring the relationship between animal welfare and empathy while considering participants' personality characteristics, it was found that empathy significantly predicted attitudes toward animal experimentation (Furnham et al., 2003).

Objectives and Hypotheses of Research

Although there are studies in the literature on the relationship between religiosity and empathy, pro-environmental behaviors, and positive attitudes toward animals, no study has been found that associates these two issues with religiosity in the same study and evaluates empathy as a mediator variable in this relationship. Accordingly, this study explores how religiosity influences empathy, pro-environmental behaviors, and positive attitudes toward animals, as well as examines the mediating role of empathy in the relationship between religiosity and both pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals. It is predicted that religiosity may affect pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals by influencing individuals' empathic tendencies. In the current study, the following hypotheses were determined within the framework of the modeling described above: (H₁) Religiosity increases individuals' empathic tendencies. (H₂) Religiosity positively affects individuals' pro-environmental behaviors. (H₃) Religiosity increases individuals' positive attitudes towards animals. (H₄) Individuals' empathic tendency increases their positive attitudes towards animals. (H₅) Individuals' empathic tendency increases their pro-environmental behaviors. (H₆) As individuals' positive attitudes towards animals increase, their tendency to show environmentally friendly behavior also increases. (H₇) There is a mediating role of empathic inclination in the relationship between religiosity and both pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals. By testing these hypotheses in this article, the aim is to contribute to the studies on the relationships between religiosity and environmental behaviors, and religiosity and attitudes toward animals. In particular, the examination of empathy as a mediating variable in the relationship between these factors is expected to make a valuable contribution to literature.

1. Method

This cross-sectional survey study aims to examine the relationship between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals, within the context of empathy's potential mediating role. Data was collected through a self-report questionnaire composed of structured scales. Data was collected using a convenience sampling technique. In the study employing structural equation modeling, religiosity was identified as an exogenous variable, while pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes toward animals were considered endogenous variables, with empathy serving as a mediating variable.

1.1. Basic Characteristics of Participants

A total of 373 students from across Turkey, mostly from Istanbul, participated in the study, some face-to-face and some online via Google Forms. Of the study group, 54.2% (N=202) were female and 45.8% (N=171) were male. The ages of the participants ranged between 18 and 49. The mean age of the sample was 24.9 years (SD=5.75). Of the participants, 79.9% (N=298) were undergraduate and 20.1% (N=75) were graduate students. Of the undergraduate students, 36.9% (N=110) were studying at the Faculty of Theology, 17.4% (N=52) at the Faculty of Engineering, 10% (N=30) at the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, while 35.5% (N=106) were studying at other

faculties (education, health sciences, etc.). Among the postgraduate students, 65.3% (N=49) were studying at the Institute of Social Sciences and 34,7% (N=26) were studying at the Institute of Health Sciences.

1.2. Measurements

1.2.1. Demographic Variables Form

The researchers added four questions to the questionnaire about the participants' gender, age, education level, and the departments they studied at the university.

1.2.2. Religiosity Scale

Religiousness tendencies of the individuals were measured with the help of the Religiosity Scale developed by Ayten (2012), which was validated and reliable. While the scale consists of nine questions and two dimensions, the researchers utilized only five questions including the 'belief-consequence dimension' of this scale in the questionnaire form. This scale measures how often individuals take religious teachings into account in making important decisions, social relationships, clothing, eating and drinking preferences, and choosing friends. The five statements that make up the measurement tool were constructed in a Likert scale format ranging from five (always) to one (never). Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were applied to the scale. According to the analysis, the exploratory factor analysis values of the scale were [KMO=.888; $\chi^2=1.572$; $p=.000$]. Cronbach's alpha value indicating the reliability of the scale was determined as $\alpha=.935$. According to the confirmatory factor analysis values, the fit indices were [$\chi^2=4.319$, $df= 3$, $\chi^2/df= 1.440$; NFI= .997; CFI= .999; TLI= .997; GFI= .995, RMSEA= .034]. There is an excellent fit in the CFA values. EFA and CFA values revealed that it was statistically appropriate to use the scale in the research.

1.2.3. Empathic Tendency Scale

In order to measure the empathic tendencies of individuals, the empathic tendency dimension of the Interpersonal Reactivity Index developed by Davis (1996) was used. Ayten (2009) took seven items from the scale developed by Davis and added two more items. This scale consisting of nine items and a single dimension was named the Empathic Tendency Scale. The scale statements were constructed in a Likert scale format ranging from five (always) to one (never).

This scale measures the empathic tendency of individuals with statements such as 'when I encounter someone who is abused, I feel a sense of protection, I can define myself as a soft-hearted person when I see someone who has been treated unfairly, I feel pity for them'. EFA and CFA were applied to the scale again. The EFA values of the scale were found as [KMO=.859; $\chi^2=1199.229$; $p=.000$]. Cronbach's alpha coefficient ($\alpha=.839$), which shows the internal consistency coefficient, showed that the scale was reliable. According to the CFA analysis data, the fit indicators were [$\chi^2= 71.664$; $df= 25$; $\chi^2/df= 2.867$; NFI= .941; CFI= .960; TLI= .943; GFI= .962; RMSEA=.071]. The CFA data were in an acceptable fit. Both EFA and CFA values showed that it was statistically appropriate to use the scale in the study.

1.2.4. Active Environmental Sensitivity Scale

This measurement tool was developed by Ayten (2010) with the aim of determining the behaviors of individuals to protect the environment. The scale consists of two sub-dimensions: "active environmental sensitivity" and "waste avoidance". The researchers included seven questions in the questionnaire form, including only the active environmental sensitivity dimension of this scale. The statements forming the scale were formed in Likert scale format ranging from five (always) to one (never).

Active environmental sensitivity includes the individual's behaviors that require active sensitivity for the protection of the natural environment such as 'attending informative meetings about environmental problems, informing people about environmental problems, participating in demonstrations protesting environmental pollution and tree planting activities, delivering batteries that have run out of energy to private organizations that collect them, using glass instead of plastic'.

Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses were conducted again to test the validity of the Active Environmental Sensitivity sub-dimension of the Environmental Behaviors Scale. According to the analysis, it was determined that the exploratory factor analysis values of the scale were [KMO=.863; $\chi^2=1089.630$; $p=.000$]. According to the confirmatory factor analysis values, the fit indicators were [$\chi^2= 26.3777$; $df= 11$; $\chi^2/df=2.398$; NFI= .976, CFI= .986, TLI=.973; GFI=.981; RMSEA=.061]. The CFA values showed an excellent fit. When CFA and EFA data were evaluated together, it was understood that it was statistically appropriate to use the scale in the research. Cronbach's alpha coefficient showing the internal consistency coefficient was found to be $\alpha= .858$.

1.2.5. Scale for Positive Behaviors towards Animals

In the study, the Scale for Positive Behaviors towards Animals consisting of eleven items and one dimension was used to determine the positive attitudes and behaviors of individuals towards animals. The scale was developed by Aysu et al. (2021). The scores of the statements in the Likert-type scale format ranged from one (I never did it) to five (I did it very often).

The scale measures positive attitudes and behaviors towards animals with statements such as 'constantly following publications about animals, warning those who throw gum on the ground to protect birds, participating in conversations about animals with pleasure, supporting giving food to stray animals, visiting animal shelters, being interested in animals, putting a container of water for animals in front of the door in summer, sharing leftover food with stray animals, taking part in the care of stray animals, taking care of stray animals and regularly buying food for them'.

EFA and CFA were conducted on the scale again. According to the analysis, it was determined that the scale had exploratory factor analysis values [KMO= .902; $\chi^2=2308.448$; $p=.000$]. According to the confirmatory factor analysis values, the fit indicators were [$\chi^2= 113.247$; $df= 35$; $\chi^2/df= 3.236$; NFI= .952; CFI= .966; TLI=.946, GFI= .947; RMSEA= .078]. The CFA data are at an acceptable level of fit. CFA and EFA data showed that it was statistically appropriate to use the scale in the study. Cronbach's alpha coefficient showing the internal consistency coefficient was found to be $\alpha=.906$.

1.3. Implementation and Statistical Analysis

The data for this study were collected from university students in Turkey in June and July 2024. The application was carried out in an atmosphere and time period when the problems caused by stray animals in Turkey were discussed by different segments of the society and a law on stray animals was enacted.

The researchers informed the participants about the aims of the study and the importance of their participation and provided necessary explanations when the participants asked some questions about the questionnaire. It took approximately 10 minutes for the participants to answer the questionnaire. Participation in the study was based on volunteering and there were no objections or problems with the questions while filling out the questionnaires.

The data were analyzed with the help of SPSS and AMOS software programs. It was understood that the kurtosis and skewness values of the research variables were within the limits of -2 and +2 and the data set showed a normal distribution (see Table 1). In other words, the data set collected from 373 people has the assumption of a normal distribution with multiple probabilistic variations. The validity levels of the scales used in the study were tested with exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, and Cronbach's alpha values were utilized for reliability. The test of the main hypotheses was carried out using path analysis in accordance with structural equation modeling. In order to determine the significance of the mediation effect, a bootstrapping process was applied with 5,000 random resampling at a 95% confidence interval.

2. Findings

In this study, descriptive statistical analysis was applied to analyze the mean values of the participants across the primary variables (religiosity, empathy, behaviors toward animals, and pro-environmental behaviors), to outline the overall profile of the study group in relation to these variables. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for Main Variables of the Study.

	Religiosity	Empathy	Behaviors towards Animal	Pro-environmental Behaviours
N	373	373	373	373
M	3.87	4.07	2.63	2.53
SD	1.10	.611	.940	.938
Range	4(1-5)	3.5(1.4-5)	4(1-5)	4(1-5)
Skewness	1.16	-.631	.513	.411
Kurtosis	.527	.511	-.361	-.453

As presented in Table 1, the mean scores indicating participants' empathic tendencies ($M = 4.07$) and religiosity tendencies ($M = 3.87$) were found to be higher than those reflecting positive attitudes towards animals ($M = 2.63$) and pro-environmental behavior inclinations ($M = 2.53$). This suggests that participants exhibited a stronger leaning towards reflecting on and attempting to

understand others, as well as adhering to religious teachings concerning daily life, including issues related to clothing and eating, in comparison to their engagement in environmental behaviors, such as participation in tree planting campaigns, addressing environmental concerns, or demonstrating positive behaviors towards animals, such as caring for and feeding them.

In the study, path analysis was conducted by means of the AMOS software based on structural equation modeling to examine the direct and indirect relations and interactions amongst the variables, as well as to examine the relevant hypotheses. In order to test the hypothesis that "religiosity influences environmental behaviors and attitudes towards animals, with empathy playing a mediating role in this process," a path analysis model with latent variables was constructed. The regression coefficients and significance levels obtained from the analysis are provided below (see Figure 1). The model fit indices, indicating the statistical adequacy of the path analysis, were as follows: $\chi^2 = 905.568$; $df = 444$; $p = .000$; $\chi^2/df = 2.017$; $NFI = .872$; $CFI = .931$; $TLI = .923$; $GFI = .865$; $RMSEA = .052$. According to the literature, NFI (Normal Fit Index), GFI (Goodness of Fit Index), TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index), and CFI (Comparative Fit Index) should be above .850 or .900, indicating that the model's fit is acceptable. Additionally, a bootstrap analysis with 5000 samples at a 95% confidence interval confirmed that both the direct and indirect effects of the model were valid and significant. Based on these findings, the model proposed by the researchers was confirmed through path analysis.

Notes: Standardized regression loadings were utilized. $^*p < .05$ $^{**}p < .001$.

Figure 1. Model for Path Analysis.

As shown in Figure 1, the regression coefficients obtained from the path analysis indicate that religiosity positively influences empathy ($\beta = .420$; $p < .001$), pro-environmental behaviors ($\beta = .255$; $p < .001$), and negatively influences positive attitudes towards animals ($\beta = -.281$; $p < .001$). Furthermore, according to the regression coefficients, empathy positively affects both positive attitudes towards animals ($\beta = .377$; $p < .001$) and pro-environmental behaviors ($\beta = .118$; $p < .05$).

Additionally, positive attitudes towards animals were found to positively influence pro-environmental behaviors ($\beta = .599$; $p < .001$). Based on these results, it can be concluded that as individuals' tendencies to support their daily lives with religious teachings increase, their engagement in environmentally friendly behaviors, such as tree planting, recycling, and supporting pro-environmental initiatives, also increases. However, their positive behaviors towards animals, such as caring for stray animals or visiting shelters, tend to decrease. Moreover, the findings suggest that as individuals' empathic tendencies increase, so does the frequency of their positive attitudes towards animals and engagement in pro-environmental behaviors. It was also observed that individuals who exhibit positive attitudes towards animals are more likely to engage in environmentally friendly behaviors.

The standardized values for the indirect effects obtained from the path analysis indicate that religiosity has an indirect predictive effect on attitudes towards animals ($\beta = .159$), while its indirect predictive effect on pro-environmental behaviors is negative ($\beta = -.024$). Bootstrapped mediation analysis indicated that empathy significantly mediated the association between religiosity and attitudes toward animals (indirect effect = .15, 95% BCa CI [.093, .235]), whereas empathy did not mediate the link between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviour (indirect effect = $-.02$, 95% BCa CI [-.123, .070]). Based on these findings, it can be concluded that while religiosity tends to reduce positive attitudes toward animals, the presence of empathy enhances these positive attitudes. In other words, religiosity, when accompanied by empathic tendencies, can have a positive effect on individuals' positive attitudes toward animals.

Discussion And Conclusion

This study aimed to determine the relationship and interaction between religiosity, empathy, positive attitudes toward animals, and pro-environmental behaviors. In addition, the mediating role of empathy in the relationship between religiosity and positive attitudes towards animals and pro-environmental behaviors was investigated. The application, which is the subject of the research, was conducted at a time when the role of individuals in combating climate change was discussed globally and regulations on stray animals were discussed on the national agenda, and the relationships between these variables, as well as empathy and religiosity, were discussed. In addition, this research aims to contribute to the related fields of study as it is the first study in literature that deals with both pro-environmental behaviors and positive attitudes towards animals in terms of their relationship with religiosity and empathy and aims to determine the role of empathy in the relationship between these aforementioned variables.

Firstly, the relationship and interaction between religiosity and empathic tendency were analyzed. The findings obtained through path analysis showed that religiosity positively affected empathic tendency. This finding supported the research hypothesis (H1) that religiosity increases individuals' empathic tendencies. When the literature is examined, it is seen that findings show that religiosity increases individuals' empathic tendencies (Ayten, 2009; Karagöz, 2022; Korkmaz&Hacıkeleşoğlu, 2021). As a result of these findings, it has been seen that individuals' religiosity is reflected in their empathic tendencies in accordance with the teachings of religions that

recommend benevolence, tolerance, and cooperative behaviors, and it has been understood that religiosity experienced in line with the teachings of religion increases individuals' empathic tendencies. This is a conclusion reached within the framework of the findings of the above-mentioned research findings based on the testimony and the findings of this study. Beyond the declarative statement, different results have been reached in studies focusing on the relationship between religiosity and empathy and its indicator, helping behaviors, by conducting field experiments (Ayten, 2017).

When the findings related to the second research hypothesis (H2) that religiosity will increase environmental behaviors are examined, it is observed that religiosity positively affects individuals' pro-environmental behaviors. The findings of Ayten (2010), Ünal (2010), and Kavalcı (2019) regarding the relationship between religiosity and environmental behaviors are consistent with the results of the present study. In the teachings of religions, nature is entrusted to people. In this context, people are held responsible for protecting the environment considering that they are both a part of nature and benefit from nature. Within the framework of the findings of this study and the studies mentioned above, it has been determined that these teachings of religion are reflected in the religious behaviors of individuals and have positive effects on their environmentally friendly attitudes and behaviors. However, in some studies on the subject, it has been found that religiosity has no effect on pro-environmental behaviors and sometimes even has a decreasing effect on them (Ayten, 2021). When all these findings are evaluated together, it is understood that the relationship between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviors will become more apparent, and the issue will be clarified by explaining the roles of other variables (such as lifestyle, personality, socio-economic status, levels of education, etc.).

The findings of this study showed that religiosity negatively affected individuals' positive attitudes toward animals. This finding does not support the research hypothesis (H₃) that religiosity will increase individuals' positive attitudes toward animals. There are also studies in the literature that do not support this hypothesis. For example, in Kafalı's (2022) study, no significant relationship was found between religiosity and some attitudes towards animals. In the study, this situation was interpreted as a change in individuals' positive attitudes towards animals due to the transmission of coronavirus from animals to humans, but the reason for this was not related to their level of religiosity. Perry and Burge's study (2019) investigated how religion predicts individuals' attitudes toward pet ownership. As a result of the study, it was found that as the rate of participation in religious practices increases, the rate of pet ownership decreases. Research shows that pet ownership is more common among people who tend to isolate themselves. The reason for this may be that these people prefer to communicate with animals to interact with people by participating in religious practices. Again, when the literature is examined, some studies are not in line with the findings of the research and that religiosity increases positive attitudes and behaviors toward animals. For example, Özen and Kartopu (2023) concluded in their study that as the level of religiosity of the individual's family increases, the level of animal-loving increases. The most important reason for this may be that religions advise loving and protecting animals. Therefore, a

high level of religiosity in the family institution, where education begins, positively affects individuals' attitudes toward animals.

In a similar study, Özen and Kartopu (2023) also found that participants who stated that they prayed continuously had higher levels of animal-loving. In his study, Bakhos (2011) explained the attitudes of Jews, Christians, and Muslims towards animals based on the sacred texts of their religions. In these texts, human beings, to whom a special position is attributed, are held responsible for nature, and animals that do not have reason and will are entrusted to humans. Therefore, religious individuals may exhibit more positive attitudes towards animals.

The research hypothesis H₄, which states that individuals' empathic tendency will increase their positive attitudes toward animals, was supported by the findings of the study. When the literature is examined, although there are studies that support this hypothesis (Demir, 2020; Demir & Zeren, 2022). Conversely, a few studies do not support this finding (Daly & Morton, 2003). The findings of this study also supported the H₅ research hypothesis that individuals' empathic tendency increases their pro-environmental behaviors. When the literature is examined, the findings of Li et al. (2024), Schreiner (2012), and Brenguer (2007) studies overlapped with the findings of this study. When all these findings are evaluated together, it is understood that empathic disposition contributes to the development of positive attitudes towards other people, animals, and the environment. In other words, an empathic disposition makes individuals more interested and sensitive to both their social and natural environment and supports them to develop positive attitudes and behaviors. Empathy skills supported sustainable behavior changes as it increased individuals' awareness of themselves, others, and nature (Hasan&Chowdhury, 2023).

The findings obtained from the path analysis supported the research hypothesis H₆ that as individuals' positive attitudes towards animals increase, their tendency to show pro-environmental behaviors will also increase. As individuals' positive attitudes towards animals increase, their tendency to engage in environmentally friendly behavior also increases because empathy and sensitivity towards animals can increase overall environmental awareness and responsibility. This may lead individuals to avoid environmentally damaging behaviors and adopt pro-environmental behaviors. Individuals adopt environmentally sustainable practices that do not harm the environment to improve the quality of life for animals. This can contribute to broader environmental protection efforts and encourage individuals to engage in environmentally friendly behaviors. A study by Kleespies et al. (2022) found that communication with animals and positive attitudes towards animals positively affect individuals' pro-environmental behaviors. Such interactions with animals increase attachment to nature and contribute to the development of pro-environmental behaviors through empathy.

The direct and indirect effect values obtained through path analysis show that empathy does not have a significant mediating role in the relationship between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviors, but empathy has a significant mediating role in the relationship between religiosity and positive attitudes towards animals. According to the findings, while religiosity decreases positive attitudes toward animals, when the effect of empathy is activated, the relationship between

religiosity and positive attitudes toward animals turns affirmative. This suggests that empathy-producing religiosity may positively affect attitudes towards animals. In addition, these findings partially support the research hypothesis (H₇).

Although it was predicted in the research model, the mediating role of empathy in the relationship between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviors could not be determined. This finding suggests that different variables may play a role in the relationship between religiosity and pro-environmental behaviors. Conducting studies to examine these variables in different studies may contribute to the explanation of the uncertain aspects of the issue.

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